

DATA FILES FOR THE ALGEBRAIC NOVIKOV SPECTRAL SEQUENCE

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ABSTRACT. This document describes the structure of some comma-separated-value (CSV) files that contain detailed information about the algebraic Novikov spectral sequence.

This document describes the structure of some comma-separated-value (CSV) files that contain detailed information about the algebraic Novikov spectral sequence. These files are auxiliary to the projects described in [1] and [2].

See the cited documents for more mathematical details. The remainder of this document describes the structure of the CSV files.

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1. h_1 -BOCKSTEIN SPECTRAL SEQUENCE FOR THE ALGEBRAIC NOVIKOV E_2 -PAGE

algNovikov-h1periodic-E0.csv Each line of the file corresponds to an element in the E_0 -page of the h_1 -Bockstein spectral sequence that converges to part of the algebraic Novikov E_2 -page. This data is used to produce the chart appearing in [2].

name: Human-readable name of an element. (Beware that naming conventions have changed over time.)

stem: The stem of an element. This is the horizontal coordinate in a standard Adams chart.

Adams filtration: The Adams filtration of an element. This is the vertical coordinate in a standard Adams chart.

weight: The motivic weight of an element.

cell: Indicates whether an element is detected by the top cell or the bottom cell of the cofiber of τ .

B means that an element is in the image in Ext of inclusion of the bottom cell.

T means that an element maps non-trivially in Ext under projection to the top cell.

shift: Used for display purposes in reference to the chart in [2], when more than one element occurs with the same bidegree. Lower values correspond to dots on the left.

h1info: Information about special behavior of an h_1 extension.

h means that an h_1 extension is hidden, in the sense that its source is detected by the top cell of the cofiber of τ , while its target is detected by the bottom cell.

p means that an h_1 extension is not known to occur.

h1target: Value of an h_1 extension. An empty cell indicates that there is no h_1 extension.

loc means that an element is h_1 -periodic.

drinfo: Information about a Bockstein differential.

An integer r means that there is a Bockstein d_r differential.

p means that a differential is not known to occur.

drtarget: Value of a Bockstein differential.

algNovikov-h1periodic-Einfy.csv Each line of the file corresponds to an element in the E_∞ -page of the h_1 -Bockstein spectral sequence that converges to part of the algebraic Novikov E_2 -page. This data is used to produce the chart appearing in [2]. This file takes the same format as **algNovikov-h1periodic-E0.csv**.

2. ALGEBRAIC NOVIKOV SPECTRAL SEQUENCE

algNovikov-E2.csv: Each line of the file corresponds to an element in the algebraic Novikov E_2 -page. This data is used to produce the chart appearing in [2].

name: Human-readable name of an element. (Beware that naming conventions have changed over time.)

stem: The stem of an element. This is the horizontal coordinate in a standard Adams chart.

Adams filtration: The Adams filtration of an element. This is the vertical coordinate in a standard Adams chart.

weight: The motivic weight of an element.

cell: Indicates whether an element is detected by the top cell or the bottom cell of the cofiber of τ .

B means that an element is in the image in Ext of inclusion of the bottom cell.

T means that an element maps non-trivially in Ext under projection to the top cell.

h0info: Information about special behavior of an h_0 extension.

h means that an h_0 extension is hidden, in the sense that its source is detected by the top cell of the cofiber of τ , while its target is detected by the bottom cell.

h0target: Value of an h_0 extension. An empty cell indicates that there is no h_0 extension.

loc means that an element is h_0 -periodic.

h1info: Information about special behavior of an h_1 extension.

h means that an h_1 extension is hidden, in the sense that its source is detected by the top cell of the cofiber of τ , while its target is detected by the bottom cell.

h1target: Value of an h_1 extension. An empty cell indicates that there is no h_1 extension.

loc means that an element is h_1 -periodic.

h2info: Information about special behavior of an h_2 extension.

h means that an h_2 extension is hidden, in the sense that its source is detected by the top cell of the cofiber of τ , while its target is detected by the bottom cell.

h2target: Value of an h_2 extension. An empty cell indicates that there is no h_2 extension.

drinfo: Information about an algebraic Novikov differential.

An integer r means that there is d_r differential.

p means that a differential is not known to occur.

drtarget: Value of an algebraic Novikov differential.

algNovikov-E3.csv: Each line of the file corresponds to an element in the algebraic Novikov E_3 -page. This data is used to produce the chart appearing in [2]. This file takes the same format as **algNovikov-E2.csv**.

algNovikov-E4.csv: Each line of the file corresponds to an element in the algebraic Novikov E_4 -page. This data is used to produce the chart appearing in [2]. This file takes the same format as **algNovikov-E2.csv**.

algNovikov-E5.csv: Each line of the file corresponds to an element in the algebraic Novikov E_5 -page. This data is used to produce the chart appearing in [2]. This file takes the same format as **algNovikov-E2.csv**.

algNovikov-Einfy.csv: Each line of the file corresponds to an element in the algebraic Novikov E_∞ -page. This data is used to produce the chart appearing in [2].

name: Human-readable name of an element. (Beware that naming conventions have changed over time.)

stem: The stem of an element. This is the horizontal coordinate in a standard Adams chart.

Adams filtration: The Adams filtration of an element. This is the vertical coordinate in a standard Adams chart.

weight: The motivic weight of an element.

cell: Indicates whether an element is detected by the top cell or the bottom cell of the cofiber of τ . An empty cell means that an element lies beyond the range that has been analyzed.

B means that an element is in the image in homotopy of inclusion of the bottom cell.

T means that an element maps non-trivially in homotopy under projection to the top cell.

p means that it is not known whether an element is detected by the bottom cell or the top cell.

h means that there is a hidden value of inclusion of the bottom cell or of projection to the top cell.

h0info: Information about special behavior of an h_0 extension.

h means that there is a hidden 2 extension.

h0target: Value of an h_0 extension. An empty cell indicates that there is no h_0 extension.

loc means that an element is h_0 -periodic.

h1info: Information about special behavior of an h_1 extension.

h means that there is a hidden η extension.

h1target: Value of an h_1 extension. An empty cell indicates that there is no h_1 extension.

loc means that an element is h_1 -periodic.

h2info: Information about special behavior of an h_2 extension.

h means that there is a hidden ν extension.

h2target: Value of an h_2 extension. An empty cell indicates that there is no h_2 extension.

3. MACHINE GENERATED DATA

algNovikov-machine.csv: Each line of the file corresponds to an element in the algebraic Novikov E_2 -page.

name: An arbitrary name assigned by machine to a generator.

stem: The stem of an element. This is the horizontal coordinate in a standard Adams chart.

Adams filtration: The Adams filtration of an element. This is the vertical coordinate in a standard Adams chart.

weight: The motivic weight of an element.

h0target: Value of an h_0 extension in the Adams-Novikov E_2 -page. An empty cell indicates that there is no h_0 extension. Beware that these are not extensions in the algebraic Novikov E_2 -page.

h1target: Value of an h_1 extension in the Adams-Novikov E_2 -page. An empty cell indicates that there is no h_1 extension. Beware that these are not extensions in the algebraic Novikov E_2 -page.

loc indicates that an element is h_1 -periodic.

h2target: Value of an h_2 extension in the Adams-Novikov E_2 -page. An empty cell indicates that there is no h_2 extension. Beware that these are not extensions in the algebraic Novikov E_2 -page.

h3target: Value of an h_3 extension in the Adams-Novikov E_2 -page. An empty cell indicates that there is no h_3 extension. Beware that these are not extensions in the algebraic Novikov E_2 -page.

drinfo: Information about an algebraic Novikov differential. An integer value r indicates a d_r differential.

drvalue: Value of an algebraic Novikov d_r differential.

REFERENCES

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- [2] ———, *Classical algebraic Novikov charts and \mathbb{C} -motivic Adams charts for the cofiber of τ* , DOI 10.5281/zenodo.6987227.

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